

NOTES

On the Synthesis and Characterisation of Titanium Tetra-*p*-tert-butylphenoxide

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SURVEY of literature reveals that aryloxy ligands have a general advantage over the alkoxide ligands in that their electronic withdrawing properties can be easily varied by changing the substituents on the ring and have been widely used in the field of organometallic chemistry related to metathesis¹ and C-H activation². Quignard *et al.*³ claimed that such ligands shall govern both activity and stereoselectivity by their electronic effects rather than their steric effect. Utility of some aryloxy complexes of tungsten(VI) as effective precursors for metathesis of olefins and catalytic properties derived from them has recently been described⁴. In view of these interesting developments associated with aryloxy ligands, we report here the synthesis of titanium tetra-*p*-tert-butylphenoxide using titanium tetrachloride and *p*-tert-butylphenol (*p*-Bu^t C₆H₄OH).

Experimental

Titanium tetra-*p*-tert-butylphenoxide, Ti(*p*-Bu^t C₆H₄O)₄ was prepared by mixing benzene solutions of titanium tetrachloride and *p*-tert-butylphenol (*p*-Bu^t C₆H₄OH) in 1 : 4 molar ratio at room temperature under anhydrous condition. The orange coloured solution was refluxed till the evolution of HCl gas ceased. An orange solid compound was isolated from the resulting solution by first concentrating it and then adding petroleum ether. The resulting solid was dried under reduced pressure. Elemental analysis established the stoichiometric composition of the compound to be Ti(*p*-Bu^t C₆H₄O)₄, d.p. 146° (Found: Ti, 7.35. Calcd. for: 7.42%). Ir spectra was recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and mass spectra on a EI-MS spectrometer employing direct sample introduction technique at 200° and excitation energy of 70 eV.

Results and Discussion

The formation of compound of composition Ti(*p*-Bu^t C₆H₄O)₄ may be rationalised in terms of the reaction,

Due to moisture-sensitive nature of the compound, melting point reported may be incorrect. Molar conductance value of 10⁻³ M solution of the compound in nitrobenzene (1.8 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) suggest it to be non-ionic. Molecular weight of the compound determined cryoscopically in nitrobenzene, suggests that it exists as a monomer in this solvent.

In the ir spectrum, the band at 3 400–3 500 cm⁻¹ (hydrogen bonded phenolic OH) has been found to disappear which suggest that deprotonation of phenolic OH group in the form of HCl gas, which is actually evolved during the course of the reaction. Significant lowering of the band at 1 225 cm⁻¹ assigned to ν_{C-O} mode by about 75 cm⁻¹ suggests a contribution from a structure of the type C–O^{δ+} = M^{δ-} resulting from drainage of electrons from the ring to the metal⁵. Bands at 588 and 580 cm⁻¹ due to ν_{Ti-O} stretching modes also confirm the coordination through oxygen of *p*-tert-butylphenoxide ion⁶. No band in the region 300–400 cm⁻¹ assigned to ν_{Ti-Cl} has been observed in its ir spectrum which suggests complete replacement of Ti–Cl bonds in TiCl₄ by Ti–O bonds.

Mass spectra of Ti(*p*-Bu^t C₆H₄O)₄ showed molecular ion peak [M]⁺ at *m/z* 644 at the expected value alongwith [M+1]⁺ peak at *m/z* 645. The base peak at *m/z* 629 has been rationalised in terms of the loss of one methyl group. Other significant *m/z* peaks assigned to different possible fragmentation species alongwith their relative abundance are given in Table 1. Similar fragmentation species have been reported earlier also in the mass spectra of related compounds⁷.

TABLE 1—MAJOR PEAKS IN MASS SPECTRUM OF Ti(*p*-Bu^tC₆H₄O)₄ AND THEIR RELATIVE ABUNDANCES

Fragmentation species*	<i>m/z</i>	Relative abundance %
[Ti(OAr) ₄] ⁺	644[M] ⁺	60
[Ti(OAr) ₃ .OC ₆ H ₄ C(CH ₃) ₂] ⁺	629 ^b	100
[Ti(OAr) ₃] ⁺	495	7.5
[Ti(OAr) ₂] ⁺	346	3.8
[Ti(OAr)(OC ₆ H ₄)(OH)] ⁺	307	22.5
[Ti(OAr)] ⁺	197	1.3
[ArOH] ⁺	150	17.5
[HOC ₆ H ₄ -C(CH ₃) ₂] ⁺	135	91.4
[HOC ₆ H ₄ CH ₃] ⁺	107	31.4
[H ₂ C ₆ H ₄ OH] ⁺	95	10
[C ₆ H ₄] ⁺	77	8.8
[C ₆ H ₅] ⁺	65	3.3
[C(CH ₃) ₂] ⁺	57	10
[C(CH ₃) ₂] ⁺	42	14

*Ar = C₆H₄.C(CH₃)₂. ^bBase peak.

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Optical Absorption and Electron Spin Resonance Spectral Studies of Copper(II) Hydroxy Ketone and Aldehyde Complexes in different Solvents

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THE present communication deals with the optical absorption and electron spin resonance studies of copper(II) complexes of hydroxy aromatic ketones and aldehydes, viz. 2-hydroxyacetophenone, resacetophenone, peonol and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde in different solvents, i.e. dioxane, dimethylformamide, pyridine and piperidine to find out solute-solvent interaction and to determine the nature of bonding in the complexes.

Experimental

The copper(II) complexes of 2-hydroxyacetophenone, resacetophenone, 2-hydroxy-4-methoxyacetophenone (peonol) and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde were prepared according to the procedures described in the literature¹. Spectroscopic grade dioxane, dimethylformamide, pyridine and piperidine were used as solvents. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-240 spectrophotometer and esr spectra (at room temperature 300 K) on a Varian E-4 X band spectrometer employing 1.25–2 gauss modulation and operating at a frequency of 9.6 GHz in different solvents at a concentration of 10^{-3} M, using DPPH as the g-marker.

Results and Discussion

The Cu^{II} complexes of 2-hydroxyacetophenone, resacetophenone, peonol, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde are coloured powders, insoluble in water but soluble in dioxane, dimethylformamide, pyridine and piperidine. All the complexes are stable in air and non-hygroscopic. Analytical data indicate that the ratio of ligand to copper is 2 : 1. Molar conductance values in nitrobenzene indicate that all the complexes are non-electrolytes in nature.

The optical absorption spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes in dioxane, dimethylformamide, pyridine, piperidine show intense charge transfer and free ligand absorption bands in the region 400–450 nm. The absorption spectra also consist of broad absorption *d-d* transitions of Cu^{II} in the tetragonal field at 14 920–15 250 cm⁻¹. The absorption band of the Cu^{II} complexes pertaining to the transition ²B_{1g} → ²E_g is lowered and appears at 14 920–15 250 cm⁻¹ in these solvents (Table 1). This lowering can be attributed to the interaction of the solvent molecules with copper(II) along the Z-axis and the extent of lowering may be taken as a measure of the donor strength of the solvent which falls in the order, dioxane < dimethylformamide < pyridine < piperidine.

In solid-state, the four-coordinated copper(II) complexes of 2-hydroxyacetophenone, resacetophenone, peonol and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde are transformed in solution into six-coordinated tetragonally distorted octahedral complexes in view of the solvent interaction with copper. Comparison of the absorption maximum values suggest that the distortion is in the order, dioxane > dimethylformamide > pyridine > piperidine, indicating that the coordinating ability of the solvents is in the reverse order. This is in agreement with the observation made by the earlier investigators².

Esr spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes in dioxane, dimethylformamide and pyridine at a concentration of 10^{-3} M consist of four absorption lines. These four lines in the multiplet correspond to the (2I+1=4) spin orientations of the copper nuclei with I=3/2. Esr spectra of the most copper(II) complexes in solution at room temperature normally